

Perfumery Chemicals from Indigenous Raw Materials*

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I am grateful to the Indian Chemical Society for inviting me to deliver the Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture for the year 1969.

During his life-time, Prof. P. C. Ray occupied a special place of pre-eminence in the social and scientific life of our country. His memory still permeates and influences our attitude towards the welfare of the community in general and the development of science in particular. He may be rightly called the leader of the renaissance of science in India. It is, therefore, indeed, a great honour for me to be associated with the name of the 'Father' of Indian Chemistry.

Prof. P. C. Ray was also greatly responsible for the development of chemical industry in this country. It will be, therefore, in the fitness of things, if I discuss in this lecture certain aspects of the production of perfumery chemicals from indigenous raw materials. Some of us may, or may not, agree regarding the usefulness of perfumery chemicals; but all the same, they are widely used as constituents of cosmetics and as food-flavouring agents. Many of these chemicals were so long being imported from abroad, mainly from the U.K., U.S.A. and the continental countries; however, due to import restrictions, imposed during recent years, it has become necessary to develop manufacturing processes for these, based on Indian raw materials and indigenous 'know-how'.

A typical Indian raw material is castor oil, the main constituent of which is ricinoleic acid. Castor oil on pyrolysis¹, either as such, or in the form of methyl ricinoleate (I) forms two major products,—heptaldehyde (II) and undecylenic acid (III). On the other hand, cracking castor soap² yields isooctanone/isooctanol (V) and sebacic acid (VI).

The chemicals so obtained from castor oil can be converted to several important synthetic perfumery chemicals. Thus, heptaldehyde on condensation with benzaldehyde forms the well-known perfumery chemical α -amyl cinnamic aldehyde³ (VII). On reaction with malonic acid in pyridin solution it gives nonenoic acid (VIII), which on cyclization in the

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1. A. S. Gupta and J. S. Aggarwal, *J. Sci. and Ind. Res.*, 1954, **13B**(4), 277; Bussy and Lecanu, *J. Pharm. Chem.*, 1857, **13**, 2.
2. Chung-Hsi Kao and Jen-Yin Yen, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **2**, 21.
3. W. C. Meuly, U.S.Pat., 1937, **2**, 102, 965.

presence of acidic catalyst is converted to γ -nonalactone (IX), known in the trade as cocanut aldehyde⁴. Heptaldehyde via stage-wise reactions (X, XI) can be converted to another useful perfumery chemical, methyl heptyne carbonate (XII).⁵

Undecyclic acid, which is formed alongwith heptaldehyde during pyrolysis of castor oil, can be cyclised to γ -undecalactone, also known as peach aldehyde (XIII), and isojasmon⁶

(XIV). Isojasmon is a cheap substitute for jasmone (XV), which is the main odorous constituent of jasmone concrete. Dihydrojasmon (XVI), which is obtained by hydrogenation of jasmone, can substitute jasmone in many perfumery compositions. It would appear that

4. a) A. Grun and T. Wirth, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2217.
b) P. Chuit, F. Boelsing, J. Hausser and G. Malet, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1927, 10, 113.
5. John H. Wotiz and Melvin S. Newman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1292.
6. S. G. Patnekar, H. H. Mathur and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 67.

for the jasmine odour certain structural features are required and that conjugated cyclopentenone and cyclohexenone systems will induce such odour, as will be evident from the examples (XVII, XVIII) cited alongwith.

Dihydrojasmane (XVI), itself can be conveniently prepared from isooctanone⁷ obtained by cracking castor soap. The raw materials and all the know-how necessary in this connection are available and could be conveniently utilized for the preparation of these chemicals under Indian conditions.

Another convenient raw material suitable from the Indian point of view, is the Indian lemongrass oil. Its main constituent is the conjugated aldehyde citral (XXII). Citral on hydrogenation can be converted to citronellal (XXIII), which on hydroxylation of the double-bond subsequently gives hydroxy-citronellal⁸. Simultaneous reduction of the aldehyde group and the conjugated double-bond present in citral leads to citronellol (XXV), which can be further converted to products like the rose oxides⁹ (XXVII). These oxides have been isolated in recent years from rose oil and, now, are established articles of the perfumery trade. Citral, on the other hand, can be reduced by using aluminium isopropoxide to geraneol^{10a} (XXVII) which is a constituent of rose oil and is also the main constituent of Indian palmarosha oil. On the other hand, citronellal can be converted to menthol^{10b} (XXVIII) for which there is great demand in the country. Menthol, thus obtained, will be optically inactive, but with a little inducement, our consumers in the perfumery trade may be persuaded to use inactive menthol in many of their preparations.

Citral in the presence of alkali and hydrogen peroxide is converted to epoxy citral (XXIX), which on treatment with hydrazine is known to form linalol¹¹ (XXX). It will be interesting and worthwhile to establish technical details for this conversion so as to make it acceptable for preparative purposes.

It is, of course, already well-established that citral on condensation with methyl ethyl ketone and acetone yields the corresponding pseudoionones (XXXI), which on cyclization will result in the formation of α , β , and γ ionones (XXXII). The proportion of a particular

8. Fox, U.S. Pat., 1967, 2, 812, 135.
9. G. Ohloff, K. H. Schulte-Elte and B. Willhalm, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1964, 47, 602; 1965, 48, 183.
10. a) V. M. Bhawe, *Ind. Perfumer*, 1958, 2, Pt. 1, 22.
b) Hashira, *Jap. Pat.*, 1957, 8875.
11. G. V. Nair and G. D. Pandit, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 5097.

isomer will depend on the mode of cyclization and the cyclising agents used. β -Ionone is an important intermediate for the synthesis of Vitamin A and other carotenoids and α and γ -ionones find use in the perfumery industry. It is also possible to convert pseudoionone to irones¹² (XXXIII). Though the steps for this preparation are somewhat involved, it is worthwhile to make efforts to prepare irones which occurs in the orris root and which finds use in delicate perfumery compositions.

A set of interesting chemicals could also be obtained from pinene. α -Pinene (XXXIV) via camphene (XXXVI) and isborneol (XXXVII) can be converted to camphor (XXXVIII). M/s. Camphor and Allied Products Ltd., of Bareilly, an industry established with foreign collaboration, is already successfully producing camphor. Incidentally, it may be pointed out that *t*-tutyl methyl ketone (XXXIX), which in its structural features resembles camphor, has a camphoraceous odour. β -Pinene on prins reaction gives nopinone¹³ (XXXV_a), which, as such and in the form of derivatives, finds use in the perfumery industry. Pinenes on the other hand can be converted catalytically to ocimene/myrcene (XXXX). These

12. D. H. R. Barton and Magdelein Mousseron-Canet, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 271.

13. J. P. Bain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 638.

hydrocarbons in recent years have proved very useful for the commercial manufacture of citral, citronellal, linalol, geraneol¹⁴ etc.

Many of the perfumery chemicals mentioned above can also be prepared in multiple steps from acetone and acetylene¹⁵. The processes involved are rather intricate, requiring specialized knowledge and may not be quite suitable for utilization under the existing Indian conditions.

There are certain other less known perfumery chemicals which could also be obtained from pinene. For example, pineneoxide (XXXXI) on treatment with certain catalysts rearranges to a 5-membered ring aldehyde¹⁶, which can be further converted to ionone type products. These appear to be finding use in perfumery preparations in the Soviet Union. Condensation of camphene/pinene with substituted phenols leads to a series of products which after further processing can be converted to useful perfumery chemicals. Such products are also finding use in the perfumery industry of the Soviet Union.

Typically Indian raw materials, obtained from turpentine oil, are carene and longifolene. These two chemicals have attracted the attention of perfumery chemists abroad, who, presumably, have been able to convert them to useful products. Though some work has been done by some of our well-known chemists in the country, it will be worthwhile for us to make further effort for their utilization for the preparation of useful perfumery

14. Paul G. Bay, U.S. Pat., 1962, 3062, 874, No. 136.
15. a) M. F. Carroll, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 704.
 b) Walter Kimel and C. Cope, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **64**, 1993.
 c) H. Lindlar, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1952, **35**, 446.
16. Z. G. Isaeva, *Zhur. Obschei Khim.*, (*J. Gen. Chem.*), 1949, **19**, 884.

chemicals. This will be an entertaining exercise for organic chemists and will also lead to results beneficial to the industry.

A class of unusually attractive compounds are the macrocyclic musks. Important members of this group are muscone (XXXXVI), civetone (XXXXVII), dihydrocivetone (XXXXVIII), exaltone (XXXXXIX), exalttolide (L), ambrettolide (LI) and dihydroambrettolide (LII). Methods for the syntheses of these compounds have been standardised by Indian workers based on easily available indigenous raw materials, such as (i) oleic acid, (ii) erucic acid from mustard seed oil, (iii) aleuritic from shellac, (iv) kamlolenic acid etc. It will be worthwhile to undertake the preparation of these compounds in our country, particularly when the relevant details are available.

There are many other perfumery chemicals indigenous manufacture for which could be easily established, provided, we have the enthusiasm and also the confidence in our ability to do so. I assume that this brief talk may be helpful in drawing the attention of those who are interested in the manufacture of such items.

I once again thank the Indian Chemical Society for inviting me to deliver this series of lectures.